

PROBLEMS OF THEORY AND PRACTICE IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: In this article, currently some problems have described which in process of learning English literature and mentioned shortly about studying as second language and new methods for teaching and its results.

Key words: reference, result, opportunity, change, native speaker, style, methods, aspect, limit, mistake, foreign, modern, literature.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТЕОРИИ И ПРАКТИКИ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКИ

Аннотация: В этой статье описаны некоторые проблемы, которые в настоящее время возникают в процессе изучения английской литературы, и кратко упомянуто об изучении как второго языка и новых методах обучения и его результатах.

Ключевые слова: ссылка, результат, возможность, изменение, носитель языка, стиль, методы, аспект, ограничение, ошибка, иностранный, современный, литература.

ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIK NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI MUAMMOLARI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hozirgi vaqtda ingliz adabiyotini o'rganish jarayonida yuzaga kelayotgan ayrim muammolar bayon etilgan va ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganish va yangi o'qitish usullari va uning natijalari haqida qisqacha to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ma'lumotnoma, natija, imkoniyat, o'zgarish, ona tili, uslub, usullar, jihat, cheklash, xato, xorijiy, zamonaviy, adabiyot

Nowadays, learning foreign languages, especially English, is developing day by day by rapid rise. As a result, in this regard, more opportunities and chances are created for kindergartens, schools and universities. The ways of teaching and learning results increasement of new language learning interest. Therefore, it is not seemed to say "wow". When knowing English was top notch news, everyone tried to acquire it however, still there are its "complications". So, what do I mean? Those who learn a certain language, those who can converse are rewarded, the salary is good, as a result as a result, blindly mastering the language caused to disappearing its literature and its main essence. Everything changes in

this world even the language because all nations study the language and talk, but they not converse as a native speaker. There two types of each language: verbal and written.

Currently, there are significant changes in this verbal style of English literature. English is used by more than 450 million people as the first language in such states as the United Kingdom, The United States, New Zealand, Canada, Australia, the former colonies of the British Empire, it is the most popular of the occidental languages. So, we know that all over the world, about 50 countries whose people speak English and these numbers can increase with new learners. We may consider several problems belongs to English and its literature of the 21st century. Despite the development of various modern methods belongs to teaching foreign languages, especially English, there are many issues in language acquisition:

Defined (limited) learning atmosphere

Insignificance in language learning

Not to leave the atmosphere of our first language

Being dependent to the teacher

Student differentiation (dominance of strong students)

One of the minor problems is that, mistakes occur as a result of the lack of a constant atmosphere of English around the language learners. Many students are not satisfied with the knowledge they have received from their teacher in the process of learning, and as a result, students look for additional information on social networks. It is known that, we do not know what kind of “person” controls his/her page of social networks (this person may be an English language specialist, or a person who is just interested in materialism, or a person who has just entered this field, or the pages of fans).

The reason is that, we do not know the level of their knowledge, the proximity of their nationality to the English nationality, and they how to teach the rules of language. Students who learning a language do not concentrate that language seriously in all aspects. Some learners focus on the speaking part of the language, and as a result, they become poor at the writing part. It is noteworthy, that very few students are engaged in the reading part of the English and its fiction, but they do not pay attention to this most difficult aspect but they are not aware of this useful part of the language. When students start learning English, they usually use listening part, and I think it is a very effective method. But doing all these aspects together plays a huge role in learning English and literature.

Another mistake we make is that, in educational institutions, foreign languages are treated as a secondary subject and are studied under compulsion. They do not want to work on themselves-read literature, write essays, exchange speech. Because learners who start studying a foreign language only, when they need to work or desire of only conversation or they are obliged by the workplace and mistakes are made in the language result of short period. As a result, it gradually affects the change of the language, the confusion of the rules, and the

written novels or something. There are phrases among the people, our sentences do not necessarily have to be grammatically correct. In my opinion, this theory is partly correct and partly incorrect. The reason is that if we constantly speak with grammatical rules, the fluency of the language will be damaged. Language learners do not and will not always follow the grammatical rules which they have learned. I think the reason why we don't know English literature is because we don't read fiction books.

Nowadays, we constantly use computer devices and do not feel the smell of books. However, book knowledge is a thousand times better than computer science. Usually, when we are learning a language, specifically when we are engaged in the reading part, we are “provided” with articles and perform tasks related to it. We know that articles are smaller than books and we only remember their meaning. But very few linguists read and analyze their language’s literature. For example, national values prevail in literature, fiction books and novels of a certain nation, but not reading these works, not analyzing them, not understanding their shortcomings and achievements causes problems in learning language and its literature. As times change, people’s outlook, lifestyle, and needs change. It can even affect the language, that is, the language can “change”.

However, it is also possible to “preserve” the language. Of course, this requires great effort and effective methods. As I mentioned above, the most effective and fastest method is to read fiction books. It is also worth noting that we should pay attention to the quality of the textbooks we use, because that source will remain in our minds. We need to work together with a team whose have the same goal, because we share ideas and experience with them. I want to talk about Benny Lewis, who speaks 12 languages, a new approach to language learning: “To learn Italian, he read dozens of grammar books, attended language courses and memorized many words, but his efforts were in vain. After that, he started learning the language by the "Listening and returning" method. After a year, he reached the level of speaking Italian fluently. He uses the same method to learn other new languages and in 3-4 months he reaches the level of communicating in a new language. As a result, a speaker of 12 languages reaches the level of linguist and translator”. It can be explained in this way, that is, the child cannot speak until 2-3 years old, and he collects new words in his mind. As he grows up, he begins to speak imitating the people around him, but no one reprimands him for his grammatical mistakes.

Children acquire their mother tongue by repeating or practicing what they hear. For every nation, its literary language is important. Because its literary language shows the presence of that people among other nations, its prestige gained over the centuries. That is why language learners whose mother tongue is different should learn the language without spoiling it while respecting the people and culture of the language they are learning. Because the main problems of literature and language are caused by language learners of other nations. What is the basis of this opinion? Because some grammar rules of the books of the past

years do not exist today. It was easy to understand the speech in movies and interviews, but it may be difficult to understand the speech in the movies of a few years ago.

In my opinion, “modern” problems of literature depend on our psychology in some aspects. There are some contradictory problems connected with language, dialects, accents, jargon, argot, slang, cant nowadays. It is necessary to give scientific definitions to the essence of the terms “globalization”, “language”, “endangered language”, accent, dialect in order to understand the core of the given research. Samuel Johnson, the creator of the first Dictionary of The English Language (1955), wrote: “Language is only the instrument of science, and words are the signs of ideas, I wish, however, that the instrument might be less apt to decay, and that signs might be permanent, like the things which they denote”. The history of English is a story of the development of language and culture during almost two thousand years. Political, social and cultural forces influenced its development bounded with the history of people who speak it. Linguists, members of endangered language communities, UNESCO and the European Union work actively to save endangered languages. Let's protect the nation, let's protect the literature, so that the literature and language of each nation will not disappear. “Successful foreign language teaching can contribute greatly to the personal growth of learners, help students to achieve intercultural sensitivity, competence, establish a willingness to understand the remarkable English language, its dialects, accents, create an open-minded positive attitude towards their own and the target cultures, pave the way for lifelong intercultural learning in all these ways”.

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